

**Proceedings of the
2019
Society of Wood Science and
Technology
International Convention**

**Convention Theme: Renewable
Materials and the Wood-based
Bioeconomy**

Edited by Susan LeVan-Green

*Overall General Chair: Eve Haviarova,
Purdue University, USA*

**October 20-25, 2019
Tenaya Lodge
Yosemite National Park, California, USA**

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Development of Nano-cellulose Based Thermal Insulating and Encapsulated Phase Change Materials for Energy Efficient Buildings

David DeVallance
InnoRenew CoE and University of Primorska, Slovenia

Abstract

Nanocellulose has been gaining more attention for use as a light-weight, bio-based, highly insulative material. Specifically, researchers and industry are looking to use waste materials, such as wood fibers, waste textiles, and under-utilized cellulosic sources for producing innovative building materials with enhanced insulative properties. In addition to insulating materials, building efficiency can be achieved through the use of phase change materials (PCMs). Organic phase change materials such as paraffin wax, polyethylene glycol, fatty acids, polyalcohol, and polyethylene have shown potential as sufficient PCMs. PCMs, especially organic based types, are generally hindered with low heat transfer rate that results in incomplete melting/freezing and losses in extraction of stored energy. Some approaches to overcome these hindrances include macro and micro encapsulating the PCMs, incorporating porous materials into PCMs, filling PCMs with highly conductive particles and fibrous materials. The overall goal of this research is to develop high performance nano-cellulose based thermal insulation material and a new generation of encapsulated PCMs with thermal conductivity-enhancing cellulose-based shells. Specifically, this presentation covers the laboratory design and development of new enhanced cellulose-based shells and the development of the encapsulation process for PCM. To evaluate the emulsification process of PCMs, heated homogenous mixtures of palmitic acid (PA) and cellulose triacetate (CTA) were prepared at 80 degrees Celsius in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). To evaluate improvement in thermal conductivity, highly conductive particles of carbon black and from carbonized wood were incorporated into shells of PCM capsules. The presentation will cover the results from the emulsification studies and improvements in thermal performance of the PCMs containing conductive carbon materials.

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